

OPEN SCIENCE GLOSSARY
2nd part
GEOSPATIAL / STANDARDS

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CF

Metadata agreements about *climate* and *forecast* (<https://cf-pcmdi.llnl.gov/>) are aimed to promote the elaboration and sharing of files created by the API NetCDF (<http://sp7.irea.cnr.it/wiki/index.php/NetCDF>). CF agreements are getting more and more attention and acceptance and have been adopted by a series of projects and groups as a primary standard. These agreements define metadata which provide a conclusive description about what the datum of every variable represents, and about its spatial and temporal properties.

This allows for users from different sources to decide which quantities are comparable and facilitates the creation of applications characterized by higher extraction capacities, *re-gridding* and visualization.

CIGNo = Collaborative Interoperable Geographic Node

CIGNo is a project which partners are CNR-ISMAR and CORILA. It is financed by the Regione Veneto with the aim to implement a data infrastructure of territorial data. This infrastructure has been then utilized within the project “Atlante della laguna” (Atlas of the lagoon) (<http://www.atlantedellalaguna.it/>).

Controlled dictionary

The term controlled dictionary indicates a series of terms under a well-defined governance and provided with features such as the non-ambiguity of the same terms, the presence of a definition for each term, the correlation between synonyms of a certain term, etc ... To get more info about the term read this article: <http://infogrid.org/trac/wiki/Reference/PidcockArticle>.

Data coverage

Coverage is synonym of *raster*, term identifying a typology of *geographic feature*.

Data raster

Unlike vectorial data, raster data are represented through an image consisting of a regular grill of pixels (cells) of variable dimensions as a function of the precision of the available datum.

EDI

EDI is the metadata editing module developed within the project “Ritmare-SP7” (<http://sp7.irea.cnr.it/>).

FOI = Features of interest

FOI stays for “feature of interest”, “freedom of information” and other definitions.

Geographic Informative Plans

When dealing with geographic data it is common to refer to “informative plans”, “informative layers”, “layer”, because the spatial part of the datum is represented over a plan. Informative plans become also layers because they can be piled one over the other.

Geoportal

The term geoportal refers to a website offering an access point to a series of digital geographic contents¹ [1]. A geoportal makes available services for research (*discovery*) and the access to different types of geospatial data and information which distributes. Each user accessing a geoportal can for example visualize different types of maps, choose them by scrolling a menu, overlap them and change their scale of representation. The user can consult the information about the map layers (informative geographic plans) and take actions on them through a series of dynamic tools (measuring distances and extensions, making SQL inquires). Thus the user can print or download the maps in different formats. The geoportal RITMARE is the site where data and information produced and collected within the RITMARE project will be found, consulted and visualized by every web user. The first prototype able to partially demonstrate the features which will be available in a future mature version of the geoportal is the RITMARE Data Portal (v0.0), consultable at the page <http://portale0-sp7.ismar.cnr.it/#/nodes/list>

To follow the development of the RITMARE geoportal it is possible to access the documentary materials provided by the research team at the internet page http://sp7.irea.cnr.it/wiki/index.php/Category:Sviluppo_Portale.

GET IT

GET-IT = Geoinformation Enabling ToolKIT starterkit[®], is the open-source software suite developed by researchers from IREA and ISMAR. It allows you to easily share maps, measurements, and sensors with simple actions. The suite is the first open-source collaborative effort toward the integration of traditional geographic information with observational data. This is achieved by coupling [GeoNode](#) with the [SOS](#) implementation by [52°North](#) and with components developed from scratch in the context of [RITMARE](#), primarily for addressing data visualization and metadata editing. URL: <http://www.get-it.it/>

Infrastructure of Geographic Data

The term infrastructure of geographic data (or infrastructure for territorial information, or Spatial Data Infrastructure, SDI) indicates the set of technologies, standards, rules and human resources needed to acquire, process, store, distribute and support the sharing of geospatial data (Federal Geographic Data Committee – FGDC, www.fgdc.gov/nsdi/nsdi.html). The concept of infrastructure of geographic data extends beyond the IT tools and services need to guarantee the access to data, and includes all activities associated to the protection of information contents and to the simplification of relations

¹ “Spatial Portals: adding value to Spatial data Infrastructures” - Tang e Selwood (2014)

between information makers and information users. The essential elements of an infrastructure of geographic data can therefore be summarized in the following three components:

- Technologic component: an SDI lies on an architecture of devices and services needed to elaborate, arrange and virtually represent geospatial data and to produce the relative metadata; this architecture includes the provision of tools to make the datum accessible to the web user;
- Legal component: the set of standards used for the distribution of data and metadata and the rules regulating the access to each resource;
- Human component: the human factors limiting the full realization of an SDI; among these, the national strategies, the legal challenges, the working priorities and the commercial interests could in fact represent a limit for the collection and diffusion of datasets (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sC-GEavq2TY>).

INSPIRE = Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe

It is the Directive 2007/2/CE from the European Parliament and the European Council of 14 March 2007, establishing an infrastructure for the territorial information in the European community (<http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>). Published in Italy on the "Gazzetta ufficiale" n. L 108 dated 25 April 2007 pages 0001 - 0014. To have a look to the Directive see also: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l7B4deyn37g>.

INTEROPERABILITY

In informatics it is the capacity of a system or of an IT product to cooperate and exchange information or services with other systems or products in free of errors, affordable, and more or less complete way optimizing resources.

KNOTS

The knot is a logic unit of an infrastructure of geographic data. Within the RTMARE project it is described by a name (*title* of the knot) and it is identical to what identifies the web services needed for the distribution of data and metadata through the RITMARE data portal (v0.0) (<http://portale0-sp7.ismar.cnr.it/#/nodes/list>). The web services are the software components needed for the representation and online distribution of resources and according to the type of resources supplied by the knot, each knot can offer more than one service.

LAYER

Term utilized to indicate geographic information plans.

METADATUM

A metadatum (from Greek *μετά* "beyond, after", and from Latin *datum/data* "information") is literally a datum beyond the datum, an information which describes the set of data.

A typical example of metadata is the sheet from the catalogue of a library. This sheet, or notepaper, includes information about the content and the location of a book, therefore about data referring to data referring to the book.

NetCDF = Network Common Data Form

It is a set of software libraries and self-descriptive "platform independent" data (independent from the operative system) for the creation, access, modification and sharing of "array oriented" data ("grilled data"), developed and maintained by the UNIDATA programme at UCAR (University Corporation for Atmospheric Research). A datum in NetCDF format is:

- Self-descriptive: a NetCDF file includes information about the data it contains;
- Portable: a NetCDF file can access from different computers (in the way they manage entires, characters, and numbers in mobile comma);
- Scalable: a small subset from a large group of data can be effectively read;
- Expandable: data can be added to a well-structured NetCDF file without copying the set of data or redefining its structure;
- Sharable: one writer and many readers can access simultaneously to the same NetCDF file;
- Storable: the access to all previous versions of NetCDF data will be supported by actual and future versions of the software.

"NetCDF" is actually defined as a format-data type especially used in science with particular reference to applications dealing with climate, meteorology, and oceanography, and also with GIS applications.

A NetCDF datum is divided into an initial part, the "header", where information describing the datum and helping its understanding through the definition of its attributes and global variables are declared, and a "body" where the true datum is stored (for example a bi-dimensional matrix).

Although the possibility to define attributes and variables in a totally arbitrary way, to fully utilize the possibilities of this data-format it is advised where not mandatory to use dictionaries and standard agreements relative to the field of analysis: for Oceanography the main references are: INSPIRE, CF (Climate and Forecast), GDS (GHRSSST Data Specification), etc ...

The use of standard and official agreements make it possible to integrate rapidly the NetCDF data-format in complex systems such as systems of cataloguing or GIS systems which offer for example the possibility to analyze and manipulate data from remote.

OSK = Observation Starter Kit

It is the module developed for the SP7 aimed at enabling the standard web services (defined by OGC) for observations.

RNDT = Repertorio Nazionale dei Dati Territoriali (National Inventory of Territorial Data)

It is the tool to search, through metadata, territorial data – and relative services – available at Public Administrations to assess their suitability in relation to predetermined goals, and to obtain indications about their access and use conditions. It represents the national transposition of the European Directive INSPIRE (<http://sp7.irea.cnr.it/wiki/index.php/INSPIRE>).

SaaS = Software as a Service

SaaS can be seen as the marketing side of the Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA). The term SaaS has become the reference term replacing the previous terms Application Service Provider (ASP) and On-Demand.

SensorML = The OpenGIS® Sensor Model Language Encoding Standard

The OpenGIS® Sensor Model Language Encoding Standard (SensorML) specifies models and XML encoding that provide a framework within which the geometric, dynamic, and observational characteristics of sensors and sensor systems can be defined. There are many different sensor types, from simple visual thermometers to complex electron microscopes and earth observing satellites. These can all be supported through the definition of atomic process models and process chains. Within SensorML, all processes and components are encoded as application schema of the Feature model in the Geographic Markup Language (GML) Version 3.1.1. This is one of the OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) (<http://www.opengeospatial.org/ogc/markets-technologies/swe>) suite of standards.

SOA = Service-Oriented Architecture

In [informatics](#) it generally indicates a software architecture suitable for supporting the use of web services to guarantee the [interoperability](#) among different systems thus to allow for the use of single applications as components of the business process and to satisfy the users' requests through an integrated and transparent way.

SOS

SOS

Example:

<http://nodc.ogs.trieste.it/SOS/sos?service=SOS&REQUEST=GetCapabilities&AcceptVersions=1.0.0>

Example:

<http://nodc.ogs.trieste.it/sos/service?service=SOS&request=GetCapabilities>)

SKOS = Simple Knowledge Organization System

SKOS is an area of work developing specifications and standards to support the use of knowledge organization systems (KOS) such as thesauri, classification schemes, subject heading systems and taxonomies within the framework of the Semantic Web.

URL: <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/intro>.

Taxonomy

A taxonomy roughly corresponds to the hierarchical organization of a controlled dictionary where the terms are correlated to more general ones (in comparison to them) (terms which appear first within a tree representation of taxonomy) as well as to more specific terms (which are going to constitute son-knots of a certain term). To get more info about the term read this article: <http://infogrid.org/trac/wiki/Reference/PidcockArticle>.

Thesaurus

Compared to a controlled dictionary or to a taxonomy a thesaurus shows a more rich referential structure where more weak relations are represented with respect to the specificity described by a taxonomy (for example the relations existing between terms which are distinct but correlated among them).

In the specific format used for the codification of thesauri which are going to be used in RITMARE (the SKOS format <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/>) these further relations include those associating terms coming from independent thesauri, important requisite to make it possible the interdisciplinary access to resources.

Vectorial data

In vectorial graphics an image is described as a pool of geometrical primitives which define points, lines, curves and polygons to which colours and also shades can be assigned. It is definitely different from raster graphics where images are described as a grill of conveniently coloured pixels.

VESK

VESK - Government assured virtual desktops - is the fastest growing provider of Hosted Virtual Desktops in the UK. It enables its clients to access all their emails, files and business applications anywhere in the world using any device. It is the only specialist hosted desktop supplier quality tested and security assured by UK Government to procure to the public sector.

URL: <https://www.vesk.com/>

WCS = Web Coverage Service

The OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) standard defines a standard interface and the operations which allow for the interoperable access to geographic coverages. The term grid coverage typically refers to contents such as satellite images, digital aerial photos, elevation digital data, and other phenomena represented by values in each measure point. Generally a Web Coverage Service is not invoked directly; client applications such as GIS-Desktop or WEB-GIS which give users interactive controls are used.

WebGIS

WebGIS are the Geographic Information Systems (GIS) published on the web. A WebGIS is the extension to the web of applications born and developed to manage the numerical cartography. A WebGIS project is different from a GIS project due to its specific objectives of communication and sharing of information with other users.

By means of the WebGIS the GIS applications traditionally developed for stand-alone users or within [LAN](#) environments can be implemented on [web server](#) (also called map-server) allowing for the interaction through internet with the cartography and its associated data.

The most well-known WebGIS examples are web applications for cartographic locationing, street maps, online atlas.

WebGIS applications can be used by means of internet browsers, sometimes by specific plugins, or through specific software such as [Google Earth](#). Other typical examples of GIS applications published in WebGIS version are the territorial information systems (SIT, [sistemi informativi territoriali](#)) of Regions and several municipalities: these provide citizens access to environmental, urban, territorial information offering a navigation based on their cartography.

WFS = Web Feature Service

The standard interface OGC Web Feature Service (WFS) allows a client for the request and import of geographical objects through the web, using independent calls from the platform. Generally a Web Feature Service is not invoked directly; client applications such as GIS-Desktop or WEB-GIS which provide the user interactive controls are used.

WMS = Web Map Service

The Web Map Service (WMS) is a specific technique defined by the OGC which dynamically produces maps of spatially referred data starting from geographic information. This international standard defines a "map" as a representation of geographic information giving back a digital image which can be visualized by a web browser. Generally a Web Map Service is not invoked directly; client applications such as GIS-Desktop or WEB-GIS which provide the user interactive controls are used.